

Depression, Anxiety and Stress among Women Prisoners Convicted for Life inside the Prison – Before and after announcement of Pre-Mature Release

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Abstract

In India, female criminality is on the rise on par with crime against women. Inside the prisons, women are found to suffer from a variety of psychological problems during the custodial tenure and this unpleasant feelings or emotions impact the level of functioning which can be experienced as depression, anxiety, stress, hopelessness and distraction, in the most extreme cases - psychotic symptoms. Hence, there is a pressing demand from the women prisoners especially the women prisoners convicted for Life point of view for early release on completion of one-third of their maximum possible sentence and on basis of good conduct inside the prison. In this context, the present study has made an attempt to identify the prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress among the women prisoners convicted for Life before and after announcement of their pre-mature release. The sample included in the study are 31 women prisoners convicted for Life of Puzhal, Vellore and Trichy Special Prisons for women (SPW), Tamil Nadu aged between 45 to 70 years who were recommended for pre-mature release by the Government of Tamil Nadu. Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS 21) developed by Lovibond & Lovibond, (1995), was translated in Tamil language and after establishing the face validity it was administered to measure the severity of depression, anxiety and stress among the women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release. Data was analyzed using ANOVA and “t” test and the findings revealed that the severity of depression, anxiety and stress was extremely severe before the announcement of pre-mature release and the severity of depression, anxiety and stress decreased moderately after the announcement of pre-mature release among the Life Convicts inside the prison. The findings implied that getting released from the prison environment and getting re-integrated to the family and society enhances psychological well-being of the women prisoners convicted for Life.

Keywords: Depression, Anxiety, Stress, Prison, Crime, Women Prisoners, Life Convicts, Pre-Mature Release

“Woman” in distant past was considered as the bedrock of a family and the society at large. Especially in India, a woman is looked upon to be a cache of social values, traditions, customs, morality and family’s harmony according to Mili, Perumal and Cherian (2015). But from

their inception, most of the women are subjected to diverse personality and physical abuse right from childhood, which continues even after they are married and become mothers when they are still very young. Once they give birth to children, they are deprived of their emotional, sexual and financial needs by their husband's and their extended family members which increases, a feeling of loneliness, insecurity and emotional trauma, which actually leads them to commit trivial and heinous crimes.

Female Criminality in India is at rise along with the increase in crimes against women as well according to the Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India (2018). To understand female criminality, it is important to ascertain the causes of why women resort to commit a crime. Bhandari (2018), states that family and primary relations are the main locus of crimes by women. Family dissolution reduces both formal and informal social control at the community level, which in turn may increase prospects for violence. Lack of love and a good relationship in the primary relationship. Disturbed primary relationships and unhappy married life are linked to crime committed by women. Therefore, the offending behavior of the women behind the bars is a response to the pain arising from personal, generational and cultural trauma. A study by Hicks and Tchaikovsky (2004), also suggested that economic gain, the attraction of money and economic reward as a pull factor, is another pathway to criminality among women. Women who had encountered harsh living conditions, disappointments in love and a large number of unfortunate experiences generally made it difficult for them to face realities of life which created emotional instability, insecurity, rejection or frustration. The distress caused by these factors is higher for women on average than for men, primarily due to blocked opportunities. Women are afraid to express anger because it could alienate those around them and so they suppress their anger and most women cope by changing anger to guilt, failure, and sadness. As result of this, the women end up in the prisons and are convicted for short term, long term and for life. Among the prisoners convicted for short term and long term, the prisoners convicted for Life undergo intensive depression, anxiety and stress because they live most of their formative years inside the prison. Most of the prisoners inside the prison undergo intensive depression, anxiety emotional stress due to incarceration because of their separation from their families and other environmental factors, is supported by a study carried out by Maschi, Viola and Koskinen (2014).

Women prisoners who are convicted for long years of imprisonment, that is women prisoners convicted for Life are traumatized about their children's future and are on a guilt trip that they may succumb to wayward habits. Of the many impact of depression, stress and anxiety experienced by the convicted women prisoners, the primary effect on the health of the women prisoners convicted for Life inside the prison was the predominant. Shrestha et al., (2017) explored the adverse effect of depression on the physical well-being of the women prisoners. The findings of the study stated that depression among women prisoners who are convicted for Life, were associated with poor self-rated health, encountering health problems, suicidal ideation and loss of weight. Following which the grueling challenges and stressful life which the convicted women experiences inside the prison events makes them less resilient. A study by Moksnes and Lazarewicz (2017) proved that due to existence of the sprawling inequalities in their access to education, healthcare, physical and financial resources, opportunities in the political, economic, social and cultural spheres, the women experience financial and emotional instability like depression, anxiety and stress before their imprisonment. After their imprisonment the life of solitude inside the prison and being away from the family is tormenting and depressing. The Life convicts inside the prison are worried and anxious about their family members outside, particularly their children and elderly parents who face social stigma because of their conviction. Another cause of their distress is that the women prisoners become apprehensive about their bail plea and release which takes a long process and also uncertain.

Most of the women who are sentenced for Life because of the type of crime, that is “Murder” or “Homicide” after their imprisonment regret for the offence they had committed and are transformed to live a modest life in future. Therefore, the “Lifer” who has completed their initial term of sentence and on the basis of their good conduct inside the prison, should be given one more opportunity to live the rest of their remaining years with their kith and kin. Therefore, the present study is conducted to identify the impact and the constructive outcomes of pre-release of the women prisoners convicted for Life inside the prisons.

Objective

To identify the impact of the announcement of pre-release on depression, anxiety and stress of women prisoners convicted for Life inside the prison.

Hypothesis

Since there were no studies related Mental Health on pre and post announcement of pre-mature release among women prisoners convicted for Life the following null hypotheses were formulated.

1. There will be no significant difference in depression among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release.
2. There will be no significant difference in anxiety among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release.
3. There will be no significant difference in stress among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release

Methodology

Sample

To comply with the objective of the present study, 31 women prisoners convicted for Life, of Special Prison for Women (SPW) of Tamil Nadu aged between 45 to 70 years, who were recommended for pre-mature release by the Government of Tamil Nadu were chosen for the study, of which 14 Life convicts from Puzhal SPW, 9 Life convicts from Vellore SPW and 8 Life convicts from Trichy SPW, were selected.

Tools

In the present study, depression, stress and anxiety was measured using the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS21) developed by Lovibond and Lovibond, (1995). The reliability of DASS-21 showed that it has excellent Cronbach’s alpha values of 0.81, 0.89 and 0.78 for the subscales of depressive, anxiety and stress respectively. It was found to have good internal consistency, discriminative, concurrent and convergent validities. The depression and anxiety subscales of DASS-21 had good correlations with self-rating depression scale and state trait anxiety inventory. The tool was translated in Tamil language and a pilot study was conducted to establish the face validity. Subsequently the tool was administered to the women prisoners convicted for Life of Puzhal, Vellore and Trichy Special Prisons for women (SPW), who were recommended for the pre-mature release before and after the announcement of the pre-mature release.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

Comparison of the Pre and Post Assessment of Depression among Women Prisoners Convicted for Life, before and After Announcement of Pre-Mature Release.

Variables	Time	n	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	‘p’ Value
Depression	Pre	31	30.52	6.89	6.01	.000**
	Post	31	15.23	11.36		

**p<0.01

Table 1 shows the impact of the announcement of pre-mature release on depression among women prisoners convicted for Life. The ‘t’ value indicates significant difference in depression among the Life convicts between the pre and post announcement of pre-mature release. The mean values indicate that after the announcement of pre-mature release, depression had significantly decreased among the Lifers. Therefore, hypothesis 1 stated as, “There will be no significant difference in depression among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release” was not accepted

Fig 1: Level of Depression among Women Prisoners Convicted for Life before and after the announcement of Pre-Mature Release

From Table 1 and Figure 1, it is inferred that there is a difference in depression among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release. The Life convicts inside the prison underwent depression due to various reasons which included their family history condition, adapting to major life changes and the chronic health problems that the inmates endured inside the prison. The most crucial reason for their grief may be the event of being sentenced as a “criminal”. Also the possible cause of depression in prison would have been the, memorizing of their past illegal acts. The Lifers constantly tend to re-live the moments of their crime, which made them feel guilty and grieved resulting to severe depression. The prolonged stay inside the prison could have also led to intense depression among the convicted because the prisoners felt loneliness, as they were isolated from their family and loved ones. Mostly living with other prisoners and the prison environment by itself to be confined to restricted space also led to depression among the Life convicts inside the prison. Therefore, after the announcement of pre-mature release of the women prisoners convicted for Life by the Government of Tamil Nadu the women convicts were overwhelmed that they would soon be united with their family members especially their children and grandchildren and would breathe freedom and hope for the rest of their life and hence there was a significant decrease in depression among the Life convicts.

Table 2

Comparison of the Pre and Post Assessment of Anxiety Among Women Prisoners Convicted for Life Before and After Announcement of Pre-Mature Release.

Variables	Time	n	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	‘p’ Value
Anxiety	Pre	31	30.65	7.03	5.82	.000**
	Post	31	15.94	11.22		

**p<0.01

Table 2 shows the impact of the announcement of pre-mature release on anxiety among women prisoners convicted for Life. The ‘t’ value indicates significant difference in anxiety among the women prisoners convicted for Life between the pre and post announcement of pre-mature release. The mean values indicate that after the announcement of pre-mature release, anxiety had significantly decreased among the women prisoners convicted for Life. Therefore, hypothesis 2 stated as, “There will be no significant difference in anxiety among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release” was not accepted

Fig 2: Level of Anxiety among Women Prisoners Convicted for Life before and after the announcement of Pre-Mature Release

From Table 2 and Figure 2, it is inferred that there is a difference in anxiety among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release. The causes of anxiety among the women prisoners convicted for Life inside the prison could be that they perpetually thought about the crime they had committed and was worried which led to mental stress. The restricted living style and being kept away from their loved ones, the isolation made them feel their loss of freedom, and thus they were pushed into a world of stress and depression. In some cases, the other inmates who co-habited with them, their unpredictable and violent character or behaviour would have created a fear in them leading to anxiety. Above all, the labelling they were given due to imprisonment, the apprehension they went through about what society would say about their term and their prolonged term inside the prison would have increased the risk levels for development of major anxiety or mental illness. Therefore, post announcement of pre-mature release among the Life convicts, the anxiety of release was replaced with hope and plans to restore family ties. The women convicts experienced great relief from the clutches of loneliness and boredom and hence there was a significant decrease of anxiety level among the Life convicts.

Table 3

Comparison of the Pre and Post Assessment of Stress Among Women Prisoners Convicted for Life Before and After Announcement of Pre-Mature Release.

Variables	Time	n	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	‘p’ Value
Stress	Pre	31	33.42	8.12	8.41	.000**
	Post	31	15.03	9.76		

**p<0.01

Table 3 shows the impact of the announcement of pre-mature release on stress among women prisoners convicted for Life. The ‘t’ value indicates significant difference in stress among the women prisoners convicted for Life between the pre and post announcement of pre-mature release.

The mean values indicate that after the announcement of pre-mature release, stress had significantly decreased among the women prisoners convicted for Life. Therefore, hypothesis 3 stated as, “There will be no significant difference in stress among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release” was not accepted

Fig 3: Level of Stress among Women Prisoners Convicted for Life before and after the announcement of Pre-Mature Release

From Table 3 and Figure 3, it is inferred that there is a difference in stress among women prisoners convicted for Life before and after the announcement of pre-mature release. The factors which caused stress among the women prisoners convicted for Life inside the prisons which adversely affected their mental health could include overcrowding, dirty and depressing environments, poor food inadequate health care, and physical or verbal aggression. Lack of purposeful activity, lack of privacy, lack of opportunities for quiet relaxation and reflection could have also aggravate mental distress and caused stress among the inmates. Reactions of guilt or shame, anxiety of being separated from family and friends and worries about the future of their children could have also compound such mental distress. Inadequate penal and judicial systems, resulting delays in access to justice and speedy trial could have also added on to the stress they were already undergoing inside the prison. Inadequate attention to the human rights of persons in the prison and the hostile treatment by the prison officials, could have further aggravated the situation. Therefore, after the announcement of pre-mature release of the women prisoners convicted for Life, the stressors like guilt, shame and boredom of being separated from their families had come to a closure, hence there was a significant decrease of stress level among the Life convicts.

Conclusion

The women who were convicted for their crime were driven by various factors like illiteracy, poverty, gender-equality, financial and emotional instability and the experience of a life of solitude inside the prison was tormenting and depressing. Although efforts have been taken by the government to improve the status of women and all that they were deprived of, it was miles away from becoming a reality to prevent the pathways that led women towards criminality and thereafter to the prisons. Hence the findings revealed that it was important that apart from community safety or punishment, one of the major roles of prisons was to provide women prisoners with opportunities for release, reformation and rehabilitation inside the prisons to promote social reintegration and prevent re-offending.

Limitation

1. The women prisoners convicted for Life who could not understand Tamil language were excluded in the study though there were few of them who were recommended for pre-mature release by the Government of Tamil Nadu.

Implications

1. The Government can show clemency and pre-release the women prisoners convicted for Life especially the old and the ailing, who have been confined for more than 10 years, based on their good conduct inside the prison, periodically on occasions like Peraraignar. Annadurai birthday and Gandhi Jayanthi.
2. The Government of Tamil Nadu can impart Life skills training to Life convicts and other women prisoners convicted for other crimes as well to reduce depression, anxiety and stress when they are inside the prison because it can alleviate the emotional problems of the women prisoners which can prevent suicide ideation when they are inside the prison and after they are released.
3. The women prisoners inside the prisons may be given individual counseling on behavioral coping strategies and emotion focused coping to regulate their emotions like depression anxiety and stress appropriately. They should also be given guidance and training on different opportunities and diverse occupations available, to manage problems arising due financial difficulties and to facilitate employment engagement at the time of their release. This could also prevent recidivism among the women prisoners inside and outside the prison.
4. The Prison Department can rehabilitate women prisoners who are mentally ill and provide the required Psychiatric treatments inside the prison to equip them to be transformed for a constructive re-integration into the society after their release.
5. The Government of Tamil Nadu can consider to implement Life Skills Training to all the Special Prisons for Women across Tamil Nadu, especially the Life convicts when they are inside the prison to empower them for better well-being when they are released.

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